

National Feeling Is The Basis Of Spiritual

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Abstract: *In the article, the author examines the concept of an educational nature based on the development of spiritual immunity. The article highlights the method of describing the ideas of courage and justice through the teaching of outstanding thinkers and philosophers of the East. The author focuses on the fact that reading literacy is of great importance when assessing the effectiveness of the educational process. It is reading that forms a national feeling, love for the Motherland in the spirit of patriotism.*

Keywords — reading, ideas of courage and justice, tradition, spirituality, immunity, harmoniously developed personality, book, independent thinking, personality, trust, kindness, national idea and ideology.

INTRODUCTION

The problem covered in the article concerns the issue of introducing into the consciousness of young people the love of reading, the art of studying books, since perseverance in reading develops logical thinking in children, broadens their horizons, and forms a feeling of love for their people, for the Motherland.

Dear mentors, instill a sense of Motherland into the minds and hearts of your pets.

From time immemorial, our ancestors adhered to the ideas of courage and justice, the teachings of Naqshbandiy “Let your hands be in work, and let Allah be in your heart.” Our national traditions and heritage are formed on the basis of the above principles. For the current generation, brought up in the spirit of national independence, these invaluable assets of our ancestors are not alien. Especially, these assets are incomparable in raising a harmoniously developed generation.

What else should we pay attention to when raising a harmoniously developed personality?

- to introduce into the consciousness of young people the love of reading, the art of studying books, since perseverance in reading develops logical thinking in children. It is necessary to teach students to respect the book. Because through respect for her, a feeling of love for one’s people, for the Motherland is formed. Respect for the book is respect for knowledge. Knowledge is the highest asset. Whoever continually acquires knowledge in order to benefit his people, his name will remain forever in history. “In order to exist in the world, secular sciences and knowledge are necessary. A nation that does not master this will be subject to strangers.” M. Behbudi.

A book is the basis of knowledge, the beginning of all beginnings. The book has such miraculous power that anyone who diligently studies it will see a window into the world open before him, into the world of inventions and laws, miracles and sacraments, treasures and mysteries. In books we find a lot of information about ways of harmonious education of the individual. With their help, we cultivate in the hearts of readers such feelings as kindness, responsiveness, and sensitivity.

There are many books in the world. What to read? Where to begin? What literature should you recommend for your

child? Your help is needed here. You need to help the child choose books, you need to teach him how to work with a book, you need to interview him after he completes each book. It is necessary to test the knowledge of the ideas and problems of a scientific, cultural, educational, economic, educational nature posed in the book. It is necessary to recommend that the child re-read individual chapters, reading and studying, reading with a pencil in his hands. A person who loves reading is not angry, he is basically decent and kind. He has a developed sense of love for his land, respect for his people.

Instill in your student that the best gift is a book.

One of the main tasks of teaching students is to teach them independent thinking, which will open up broad prospects for them in choosing their future.

To explain the topic, the teacher collects a lot of information, substantiates it with additional materials, and prepares for the presentation. What are the results of this training? Is this interesting to the student? Did he understand everything? We need to find answers to these questions.

If you want to give solid knowledge to your student, then you need to change your approaches, methods and forms of your activities. Here pedagogical technologies will come to your aid: “Debates”, “Brainstorming”, “Round Table”, “Presentation”, “Ring” - this is a range of innovative methods that activate students, developing their independent thinking, guiding them towards independent search. In order to find answers to questions, the student will directly turn to books and study them.

Feeling of Motherland... How precious and priceless it is. It is as dear as your own mother. A person has one mother, one homeland. We were born and raised in it. Therefore, it is dear and sacred to us. We must cultivate this great feeling so that our children grow up to be patriotic and harmoniously developed. Introduce them to the great past, the rich heritage of our ancestors. Educate them in the spirit of humanism and devotion to the Motherland

An important role in the formation of positive qualities between teacher and student is cooperation between them. Trust based on mutual respect and kindness brings good results. Faith in one's teacher and one's abilities dispels excessive anxiety and hopelessness in a student, dulls pride, and warns him against negative actions. Each child is a unique

personality. The teacher who tries to educate his pet according to ready-made canons and recipes is mistaken.

Pedagogical theory is not a dogma. Observations, experience, generalizations and conclusions and, finally, experiment - these are the components of the theory of education. Study the psychophysical characteristics of the child, draw scientific conclusions that are ahead of the curve, then you will be able to predict and prevent negative phenomena in your pet.

Educators must take their responsibilities with great responsibility in order to prepare themselves for the great mission. They have to:

- deeply understand and assimilate the meaning of ongoing economic reforms, national ideas and ideology;

- know universal and national values;

- find effective and efficient methods and forms of introducing into the minds and hearts of their students a sense of patriotism and humanism, faith in the bright future of the country;

- to form in students a healthy lifestyle, hard work, national pride, internationalism and humanism, courage and bravery, creativity and curiosity;

- scientifically substantiate the age characteristics of children, the content of knowledge, skills and abilities;

- successfully use innovative technologies in the educational process;

- teach students to think independently, draw conclusions, evaluate situations and phenomena, teach cooperation, respect for other people's thoughts, confidentiality;

- cultivate a sense of mutual assistance and assistance, activity in classes, skills in using laboratory equipment;

- have the skills to use technical means, information and communication technologies;

- ensure cooperation between school, family and mahalla committees;

- be able to analyze the effectiveness of teaching work;

- be able to deeply explain the historical and modern essence of the development of sciences;

- deeply assimilate secular and social knowledge, form your own point of view;

- be able to use Internet services;

- objectively evaluate the knowledge, skills and abilities of their students, as well as control;

- deeply understand the principle of the unity of teaching and upbringing.

In conclusion, I would like to summarize what was stated in the words of the famous educator A. Avloniy: "Education for us should be a matter of life or death, hope or collapse, happiness or disaster."

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